

Echocardiographic Evaluations of Tetralogy of Fallot in Children Under 16 Years of Age at Children's Hospital

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Abstract

Background: The TOF term was firstly described by the Danish anatomist Neils Stensen, in the year 1671 observed in a fetus suffering from ectopia cordis. In the year 1888, a series of 5 reports that described the four anatomical features occurring in a particular group of patients suffering from cyanosis was given by Etienne louis Aurthur. The combination of this tetrad described by him is given as, Ventricle septal defect, Pulmonary stenosis, Right ventricular hypertrophy, Overriding of aorta. This combination tetrad described by him was known as the Tetralogy of Fallot. It was named as la maladei blue i.e [the blue malady].

Objective: To evaluate the findings of Tetralogy of Fallot in children through echocardiography.

Materials and Methods: It's a retrospective study in which a total of 88 patients who visited cardiology department of Children's hospital for echocardiography examination were taken. An echocardiography test is performed to evaluate the frequency of Tetralogy of Fallot.

Results: This study had 88 patients, who fulfilled the criteria were taken, out of which 60(68%) were male and 28(31%) were females. Out of these 88 students, 84% patients have Tetralogy of Fallot disease and tetralogy of Fallot was absent in 16% of the patients.

Conclusion: The Tetralogy of Fallot is related to various anatomical differences and in order to avoid further surgical complications there is a necessity to get it identified. Echocardiography can diagnose these anomalies in a much better way and it has helped greatly to reduce the need for invasive procedures like cardiac catheterization for these patients.

Keywords: Echocardiography, TOF, VSD, PS, RVH, Aortic Overriding.

INTRODUCTION:

Tetralogy of Fallot (TOF) is the greatly common cyanotic congenital heart disease accounting for 3.5% of all of them occurring in infants and children congenital. It may be called as "Steno-Fallot Tetralogy". The sign and symptoms of this disease depend on the severity of obstruction of the RVOT (Right Ventricular Outflow Tract) Obstruction. It is a by birth disorder leading to following four anatomical complications: biventricular aortal origin, pulmonary stenosis, right ventricular hypertrophy and an interventricular defect.^[1]

Now for the pertaining global circumstances, TOF is considered universally accepted for surgical repair resulting in long-term positive prognosis. However, there is a need for a complete anatomical description prior to surgery. It is an anomaly by birth being caused by the combination of four cardiac anatomical defects.^[2]

Ventricular Septal Defect (VSD)-Normally the Septum between two chambers of heart stops mixing blood between two sides of heart. Basically this abnormality is defined a hole in the heart

septum which leads to the oxygen poor blood in right ventricle to intermix with the oxygen rich blood in left ventricle.^[3]

Overriding of Aorta- Aortic overriding is explained as the high-oxygenated blood carrying artery from heart to the body is displaced or dispositioned from its normal anatomical position and instead of being present just above the left ventricle as present in a normal healthy heart, it is present above the both ventricles, resulting in the dispositioning of the mal-aligned cardiac outlet septum into the right ventricle and the root of aorta start overriding the muscular septum of the ventricle.^[4]

Right Ventricular Hypertrophy- Due to the right side of the heart draining excessive blood flow from the left side of the heart, it works harder and the muscular wall of the right ventricle gets abnormally thicker through the ventricular septal defect.^[5]

Pulmonary Stenosis-The outlet septum's antero-cephalad deviation, along with the abnormal relationship to the septo-parietal-trabeculations, causes the narrowing of sub pulmonary outflow tract.^[6]

When interrogated with Doppler, the Echocardiography diagnoses the intracardiac anatomy of patients with TOF very accurately. Echocardiography is very accessible and reproducible non-invasive Imaging technique in detection of Tetralogy of Fallot.^[7]

Rationale:

This purpose of this study is to explore the radiological findings related to cardiac anatomical abnormalities due to tetralogy of Fallot in children with the help of echocardiography because it has been proved to be the most valuable non-invasive tool in assessing the proper parameters

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design: Observational and Descriptive only. **Settings:** The study was conducted at the Children's Hospital Lahore. **Duration:** The duration of this study was 4 months from October 2021 to February 2022. **Sample Size:** The sample size calculated was 88 during the period of four months. **Sampling Technique:** The sample was calculated using convenient sample technique.

Inclusion Criteria: Pulmonary Stenosis, Ventricular septal defect, Thickened wall of right ventricle, Misplaced aorta, Confluent PAs, Aortic Arch.

Exclusion Criteria: All other diseases excluding tetralogy of Fallot. **Data Collection Procedure:** It is a retrospective study of children diagnosed with tetralogy of Fallot. Data is taken from radiology department of Children's Hospital Lahore. Almost 80-90 cases diagnosed with tetralogy of Fallot included in this study. Data is entered using IBM-spss v-23 software; most appropriate statistical tool used to analyze the data. The continuous variable is expressed as mean±S.D and categorical data expressed in the form of frequency and percentage. A value of less than 0.05 will be taken as p-value statistical significance. Various graphs will be used to display data. The outcome measure for there of this study is Tetralogy of Fallot. **Statistical Analysis:** Data was entered using IBM SPSS V23 Software. The continuous variable was expressed as mean±S.D and frequency & percentage was used to express the categorical data. P vale less than 0.05 was taken as statistical significance. Various tables were used to display the data. Outcome measure was to detect Tetralogy of Fallot. This study is approved by our institutional review board.

Ethical approval: The study is approved by the review board of our institution.

Results:

In this study of 88 patients, who fulfilled the criteria were taken, out of which 60(68%) were male

and 28(31%) were females. Bar charts are used to display the data. Bar charts are used to display the data.

Table 1: Table showing gender distribution

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	60	68.2
Female	28	31.8
Total	88	100

In this study of 88 patients, who fulfilled the criteria were taken, out of which 62% were of age group 0 to 5 years, 28% were of age group 6 to 10 years and 5% were of age group 11 to 16 years

Table 2: Table showing age distribution

Age of Patients	Frequency	Percentage
0 to 5 years	55	62.8
6 to 10 years	28	31.8
11 to 16 years	5	5.7
Total	88	100

In this study of 88 patients, who fulfilled the criteria were taken, out of which 84% were diagnosed with TOF and TOF was absent in 16%.

Table 3: Table showing TOF findings

Tetralogy of Fallot Findings	Frequency	Percentage
Present	74	84.1
Absent	14	15.9
Total	88	100

Discussion

In this study of 88 patients, out of which 60(68%) were male and 28(31%) were females who fulfilled the criteria. Out of these 88 patients, Tetralogy of Fallot was present in 84% and absent in 16%. Referring to Aso Faeq Salih, who carried out a study on echocardiographic morphological evaluation of tetralogy of Fallot in Iraq and Kurdistan. Study included 308 cases. Among 205 were children, 86 infants, 14 adult and 3 cases were of neonates. Some associated lesions were found with Tetralogy of Fallot like patent ductus arteriosus, ventricular septal defect, atrial septal defects, aortopulmonary collaterals and aortic regurgitations. Out of 308 cases of Tetralogy of Fallot, 125 were operated^[9]. Referring to Habibullah Yadollahi Farsaniudy who conducted a study on the characteristics of tetralogy of Fallot in Iranian patients. Study included 60% Males and 40% females. Patent foramen Ovalle, Right aortic arch, coronary artery anomalies and other anomalies incidence were 44.81%, 21.11%, 9.25% and 36.30% respectively^[10]

Conclusion

The Tetralogy of Fallot is related to various anatomical differences and in order to avoid further surgical complications there is a necessity to get it identified. Echocardiography can diagnose these anomalies in a much better way and it has helped greatly to reduce the need for invasive procedures.

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